

A qualitative research on entrepreneurship, the psychological capital and integration of the refugees resettling in Scotland

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In recent years, the world has faced significant challenges related to the large-scale displacement of refugees and the subsequent issues of resettlement. Promoting refugees' economic independence through employment and self-employment remains a key strategy for facilitating their integration into host countries. This research explored the experiences and perceptions of entrepreneurship, psychological capital, and integration among refugees resettling in Scotland. A qualitative approach using interpretative phenomenological analysis was employed. Five refugees participated in semi-structured interviews. The findings revealed that unemployment upon arrival negatively impacted their sense of self-worth. However, a strong desire for self-actualisation was evident among both refugee entrepreneurs and latent entrepreneurs, serving as a key motivation for pursuing entrepreneurship. Valuable assets such as extensive work experience and psychological capital were identified as critical for entrepreneurial success. Furthermore, the asset-focused entrepreneurship education provided by the Blue Social Programme was found to have a potentially positive impact on the psychological capital of refugees with entrepreneurial aspirations or those starting their own businesses.

Keywords: entrepreneurship; integration; psychological capital; refugee; self-actualisation

Integration for refugees is regarded as a successful product of resettlement, marked with comprehensive achievements in various dimensions including legal, economic, and social (Ager & Strang, 2004; United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees [UNHCR], 2017). Accomplishments in employment, housing, education, and health are believed to serve as both means and marks for successful integration (Ager & Strang, 2004). Apart from being employed in the new communities, establishing enterprise is increasingly recognised as an effective approach for refugees to overcome some of the challenges that might occur with their economic or social attempts to merge into the new life (United Nations Conference of Trade and Development [UNCTAD], 2018). However, there is a scarcity in the literature regarding refugee entrepreneurs. Therefore, the present research will focus on the lived experience of the refugee entrepreneurs resettling in Scotland, UK.

To enhance clarity, it is important to define key terms central to the study. Self-efficacy is understood as the confidence in one's ability to succeed in specific situations (Bandura, 1997), while hope refers to a positive motivational state based on goal-directed energy and strategies to achieve these goals (Snyder et al., 1996). Integration is defined as the process of becoming part of the host society, encompassing social, economic, and cultural dimensions (Ager & Strang, 2004). Entrepreneurship support is described as the resources and assistance provided to enable individuals to start and grow businesses (UNCTAD, 2018). These definitions ensure that discussions remain consistent and clear throughout the paper. By integrating these concepts, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of their influence on the experiences of refugee entrepreneurs in Scotland.

Refugee entrepreneurs make contributions to the host society, emphasising roles such as local job creation, fostering innovation, and enhancing cultural diversity (Wauters & Lambrecht, 2008). Their entrepreneurial activities not only enrich the local economy but also align with policy frameworks that support economic integration and social cohesion (UNCTAD, 2018). Additionally, the notion of "transition stress" is intricately linked to psychological capital, encompassing aspects such as resilience and self-efficacy, which are crucial for overcoming challenges and achieving entrepreneurial success (Luthans et al., 2007). By examining how participants use these attributes to navigate transition stress, the study provides a deeper understanding of individual strategies to build psychological capital and resilience during periods of change (Bandura, 1997). This analysis offers insights into how refugee entrepreneurs contribute to and integrate within the broader societal and economic landscape.

Promoting entrepreneurship is increasingly recognised as an effective approach for refugees to overcome some of the challenges that might occur with their economic or social attempts to merge into the new life (UNCTAD, 2018; Wauters & Lambrecht, 2008). Entrepreneurship provides socioeconomic opportunities for refugees to integrate into the local economy, through which they could share their experience, skills, entrepreneurial spirits, build new networks and create more working opportunities for the market (UNCTAD, 2018). However, lower levels of language proficiency, perceived discrimination by employers, and failure to enter the local labour market constrain the development of entrepreneurship (Garnham, 2006; Lyon et al., 2007; Rajman & Tienda, 2003; Wauters & Lambrecht, 2008). To overcome these salient barriers and obstacles, support through various programmes on refugee entrepreneurship has been provided by the government and service organisations in different countries (UNCTAD, 2018). Approaches and activities of the entrepreneurship support programmes mainly cover business skills training and coaching (e.g., Jumpp [Germany]), incubators and job-matching initiatives (e.g., Startup Refugees [Finland]), business planning, and technical assistance schemes (e.g., Entrepreneurship Support Program for Refugee Empowerment [ESPRE], Japan).

In addition, one of the assets that can promote entrepreneurship is psychological capital (Envick, 2005). Psychological capital (PsyCap; Luthans & Youssef, 2004) refers to an individuals' positive psychological state and comprises hope (Snyder et al., 1996), optimism (Carver & Scheier, 2003), resilience (Tugade et al., 2004) and self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997). Hope is a positive state including belief in achieving a goal and ability to have identified specific ways to that goal (Snyder et al., 1996). It is also regarded as a coping strategy to handle stressful events (Alexander & Onwuegbuzie, 2007). Optimism refers to a positive attitude toward challenges and future success (Carver & Scheier, 2003).

Resilience refers to an ability to adapt and bounce back from adverse events (Tugade & Fredrickson, 2004). Self-efficacy means that a person has confidence in his/ her ability to undertake tasks. People with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to set and persist on challenging goals, recover quickly from frustrations and experience higher life satisfaction (Bandura, 1997). These four factors are clustered for PsyCap because they all reflect a positive appraisal of the current situations and the future chances of success (Luthans et al., 2007). It is more of a state rather than a psychological trait, for it involves thoughts and actions that can be more flexibly acquired and developed by anyone. There are numerous studies of PsyCap in the context of workplace management. It is regarded as a valuable asset for an organisation in addition to human and financial capital (Envick, 2005; Luthans & Youssef, 2004) and has been found to be positively related to leadership and entrepreneurial efficacy, career decision-making and turnover, learning in the workplace, and coping with perceived stress (Luthans et al., 2007). For entrepreneurs, research has shown the importance of psychological capital in terms of business performance (Hmieleski & Baron, 2016; Hmieleski & Carr, 2008), leadership (Jensen, 2006), and well-being (Hmieleski & Carr, 2007).

Despite research on PsyCap of refugee employment (e.g., Newman et al., 2018; Pajic et al., 2018), there is a dearth of research on PsyCap of refugee entrepreneurs. Thus, this research will investigate the Blue Social Growth Entrepreneurship Project provided by the Scottish Refugee Council, the Scottish Islands Federation and Community Development Lens (CoDel). The asset-oriented project is designed for the migrants and refugees in Scotland to help the latent entrepreneurs recognise and employ their personal, environmental and social assets to start their own business. By interviewing the participants, the research will explore what's the experience of the refugee entrepreneurs and latent entrepreneurs and the influence of the workshop.

Specifically, this research aims to explore the refugees' experience of entrepreneurship and its role in enhancing refugees' integration process, perception of psychological capital and entrepreneurship support. In particular, this study focuses on these research questions: (1) What are the refugees' experience of entrepreneurship in the host country? (2) What are the refugees' experience of psychological capital in their business? (3) What are the refugees' experience of their participation in the Blue Social Growth Project?

METHODS

Design

This qualitative research used Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA; Smith et al., 1999). Data was collected with semi-structured interviews. IPA focuses on the participants' experience, stories and insights of an event rather than the objective definition (Smith, et al., 1999). It allows the researchers to understand participants' perspectives and interpret their words through different layers. Since it could provide information that cannot be found with quantitative methods, IPA is widely used in refugee research (Schweitzer & Steel, 2008).

Participants

Recruitment was conducted with help of the Scottish Refugee Council, whom the refugees had direct contact with. The Participant Information Form and inclusion criterion were provided by the research team to help the Scottish Refugee Council communicate with the refugees. The inclusion criteria were: 1. over-18-year adults 2. able to communicate in English 3. working on or willing to start a business here in Scotland. After communication, the Scottish Refugee Council facilitator replied that five refugees would like to participate and provided their contact information to the research team. Three of the participants were males and two were females. Ages ranged from 36 to 50 years old ($M = 44$), with one participant's age not disclosed. The duration of resettlement in the UK until the interview ranged from 14 to 24 months ($M = 18.8$). Two of them were working on their own business. The rest of the participants were unemployed but had entrepreneurship intentions.

Data collection

Data was collected with in-depth semi-structured interviews. The interviews took place online via Zoom and WhatsApp according to the participants' preference. The lengths of the interviews ranged from 63 to 104 minutes and the average was approximately 80 minutes.

Interviews sought to elicit detailed accounts of the participants' experience and insight in three domains: employment and entrepreneurship prior to and after their migration to the UK, PsyCap and integration. Given the focus on phenomenology and lived experience, the interviews avoided using a priori questions but encouraged participants' free narratives in their own way and time (Ghorashi, 2008), which is particularly useful when the previous and current lived experience are interweaving (Terjesen & Elam, 2009).

The interview transcripts were anonymized, encrypted, and stored in the University's system. The audio records were deleted permanently after transcription. Level 2 ethical approval was obtained from the University of Edinburgh, School of Health in Social Science Ethics Committee, prior to participants' recruitment and interviews. All participants signed an informed consent.

Analysis

Analysis followed the instructions in the article of Smith and his colleagues (Smith et al., 1999). Transcripts were imported to NVivo programme for coding. In the first step, the first participant's transcript was read carefully many times while notes of any keywords were taken. These keywords revealed the participant's feelings, thoughts, behaviours, etc. All information was paid equal attention to, without omission or neglect. After close inspection of the transcripts, common themes and the connections between them emerged, roughly producing a preliminary theme list, which was used in the analysis of the subsequent transcripts. Each transcript added new content into the preliminary list, expanding the existing themes, and adding new themes at the same time, before creating clusters for related themes. The patterns and relationships between the clusters were further explored, focusing on the themes commonly shared by the participants (Smith et al., 1999).

Reflexivity

In acknowledging the importance of reflexivity, this study recognises how the researchers' backgrounds and beliefs may have influenced the research process (Finlay, 2002). The researchers actively explored their personal beliefs through reflective journaling and discussions, considering how these might impact data collection and analysis. They also examined cultural backgrounds and professional experiences to understand potential biases. Awareness of power dynamics was addressed by fostering an open dialogue with participants and ensuring they felt empowered to share their perspectives freely. Strategies such as peer debriefing and member checking were employed to mitigate biases (Creswell & Poth, 2018). By actively reflecting on these factors, the study aims to maintain credibility and transparency, ultimately strengthening the overall integrity of the findings (Berger, 2015). These measures ensure a rigorous approach, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences. The research team recognises that our background provides us with certain privileges and biases that may shape the way we engage with participants and interpret their perspectives. Throughout this research, we were aware of the power dynamics and position of authority as researchers. We strived to minimize power imbalances by creating an open and respectful environment for participants to share their experiences. We aimed to be reflexive throughout the research process, continually questioning how our own assumptions, biases, and positionality may influence the research outcomes.

The study was conducted with a commitment to authentically understanding the lived experiences of the participants. However, it is acknowledged that the interpretations are inevitably influenced by the researcher's own subjectivities. During the interviews, the researcher avoided taking ideas for granted by clarifying vague words or sentences and encouraging participants to fully explain their thoughts. During the analysis, efforts were made to stay as close as possible to the participants'

perspectives, understanding their stories within their unique contexts, and identifying both individual experiences and shared themes. To minimise interpretative bias, two methods were employed: critically reflecting on the analysis process and sending the master list of themes to participants for their comments and reviews.

RESULTS

The participants' accounts clustered around three superordinate themes: the experience of entrepreneurship, transition issues and integration.

Table 1
Super-ordinate themes and sub themes for the IPA

Super-ordinate themes	Sub themes
1. Transition issues and integration: from previous identity to a refugee	1.1 Unemployment and the threatened self-value and self-identity 1.2 Lacking in networks and their endeavours to networking
2. The experience of entrepreneurship and integration	2.1 Rich working experience 2.2 Self-actualisation 2.3 Benefiting the host society
3. The experience of psychological capital and the entrepreneurship education	3.1 The role of psychological capital in entrepreneurship 3.2 Entrepreneurship education: The Blue Social Growth programme

Transition issues: from previous identity to a refugee

Unemployment and the threatened self-value and self-identity

All the participants experienced or were experiencing stress during the transition to refugee life, including social identity (from a citizen in one's home country to a refugee in a host country), loss of income, reduced living quality, changes of family responsibility, etc.

Much of the stress came from unemployment. Unemployment status did not only bring emptiness, but also compromised their self-identity: from an independent social person creating values to an unemployed person who has to depend on the government. This state does not correspond with their expectation for themselves which may have a negative effect on their mental well-being, but also serves as a motivator to work. Occupational achievement is not only about personal fulfilment but also a social acknowledgement.

Participant 1: "When we came here you are feeling in this empty space. We have many experiences, 21 years' continuous working. But when we came here waiting and wasting time, doing nothing, it was affecting our morality negatively. Creating new business is good for our mind and also contribute to this country for doing your experiences. Actually it gives us morality."

Participant 5: "Now we think we are not good we are depending the government, but we think we need to be independent from the government and earn more money."

The stress also comes from the discrepancy between one's capability and the unsatisfactory job. All of the participants had successful careers before they migrated to the UK. When they were not accepted in their familiar area, not able to get a satisfactory job as before but have to be underemployed, their self-worth could not be realised, which would be stressful.

Participant 1: “I applied for some job opportunities. They replied that you are overqualified. So it’s very awkward. You have more experience but sometimes it’s negative things.”

Participant 5: “Job centre said to me ‘you should go to elsewhere; you should go to the coffee shop and you should go to the hotel.’ But I said no because I need time to improve my English. I am an art teacher in my home country.”

Being unemployed, they chose to do voluntary jobs in their professional areas to achieve self-actualisation. For Participant 5, volunteering brought her an opportunity to display her paintings, which became a precious moment of fulfilment, though the exhibition was not for sale and there were no financial rewards.

Participant 3: “This is my first exposure to voluntary sector, that sector of the economy. I find it more fulfilling than being just working in the private sector.”

Participant 5: “And it encourage me. I was so so so happy for this exhibition. Because some of the people they said to me ‘oh it’s painting I thought it was photography!’ I said no it’s painting. It was very nice.”

Lacking in networks and their endeavours to networking

Networks are highlighted by all of the five participants in their search for jobs and entrepreneurship chances. Lack of networks with the local people is regarded as the major barrier for refugees’ entrepreneurship. As an important asset left in the country of origin, networking should be re-established and could be a real challenge for the refugee entrepreneurs.

Participant 1: “Creating network is the first.”

Participant 3: “The biggest challenge will be the lack of a network to start off with...”

Participant 5: “Now I don’t know how can I speak to an artist here. Maybe they [refugee service providers] can help me introduce to another artists here in this country.”

To establish networks, the participants have made various efforts. First, going to a local college is a common choice, though they’ve already finished their university education many years ago in their countries. In the local colleges, Participants 1 and 2 learned similar even the same subjects as before. For them, networking, instead of knowledge, is the key concern and crucial function. Participant 4 does not worry about co-workers in his business because he has already met them in college.

Participant 1: “I continued study to improve my English at the college because I already know the things, the subject e.g., web designing and other things. It’s also important to build new network. It’s important thing.”

Participant 2: “So I also decided to go to college... I know many people from here, so you get to know them, their thinking and culture, how they reason, how they do their things. That’s important. It makes integration easier.”

Participant 4: “For me it’s easier because I have my group mates. I have my college, university, so that’s my main source of colleagues.”

Second, doing a voluntary job is believed helpful for networking. Participant 1 volunteers to provide IT support for his community, through which he can build networks and find business opportunities. Participant 5 volunteers in the museum, gallery and church, doing art-related works, which helps her gain experience, knowledge of local customers’ demands and vocational references.

Participant 1: “I started [integrate into] this community with IT support; it’s a volunteer thing and then you can meet people in the community and grow my business.”

Participant 5: “...when I go to the Kelvingrove museum then Modern Art Gallery said to me, called to me that can you come for do some voluntary on Saturday morning for children.”

Networking and mutual understanding with the local people are also highlighted in refugees’ vision of integration.

Participant 1: “Then meet local people, another friends, joining the communities, working and sharing something.”

Participant 2: “OK well first to integrate you have to understand the people, right? I know that’s very very important thing.”

Participant 3: “Integration for me would be that I grow a network of people that I met through my work, or social gatherings, or when I know I can... exchange thoughts freely with, you know people I can understand and they understand me.”

Since their arrival in the host country, they have experienced transition stress around sense of losing self-worth, social identity changes, different and difficult daily life, mainly brought by unemployment and their refugee identity. They have made various efforts to tackle the transition issues such as doing voluntary work, going to college, job hunting, and entrepreneurship.

The experience of entrepreneurship

Rich working experience

All of the five participants have a long time of working experience before their migration. The working experience plays an important role in career choice for these individuals. It helps them think about which occupational field and which role (employee or entrepreneur) are suitable. For those who intend to continue working in their familiar area, it provides a professional foundation for entrepreneurship.

Two of the five participants, Participants 1 and 2, have already been working on their own business in the host society. Both of them are doing businesses closely related to their previous work. Participant 1 is a senior engineer with over 20 years of experience in the information and technological (IT) field and he is developing an e-learning business now. Participant 2, with 15 years’ experience in catering and successful entrepreneurship of his own restaurant before migration, has finished a business proposal for his restaurant in the new society. Participant 3 and 5 also have rich experience in their field of speciality and hope to continue their expertise in the future.

Participant 2: “I worked for many years, 15 years in restaurant business as a manager. I once have my own business. It was quite successful. Very good yeah. So I want to do something like that, getting a restaurant of my own.”

Participant 3: “...once you being an entrepreneur, it’s not easy to forget that. You’ll find yourself...you have that mindset. Naturally, leaving my entrepreneurship roles back home, [I] come over here. But at the back of my mind, sometime in the future, I do hope I have the opportunity to become an entrepreneur again, to do something for myself.”

Participant 5: “Maybe I can have some workshop for make money. Maybe I can get some money from the government and start self-employ about art, e.g., I open a gallery and show some of my painting.”

Self-actualisation

To realise and display self-value is a major expectation and motivation for entrepreneurship in addition to financial incentives. It is also regarded as an important component in the participants' vision of integration.

Participant 1: "As I mentioned you need to show your abilities, what's your expertise. Show them so you can start and continue growing your business."

Participant 2: "Secondly, it's realising my goal. My goal is to have my own. Working for somebody, that's somebody else's goal."

Participant 3: "But once those [basic] needs are being taken care of, you'll start moving on to choose doing other things that are deeply important to you."

Participant 4: "Self-realisation, I think. For me, integration means that I will spend quality time with my business ideas, with my study, that I'll become professionally stable, I think that's the most important thing..."

Benefiting the host society

In addition to self-actualisation, the refugee entrepreneurs and latent entrepreneurs hope and believe that they can make a contribution to the host society with their own businesses. In their perspective, they could contribute to the local economy by: 1. providing goods and services to fill market gaps 2. providing jobs 3. being financially independent to reduce the government's economic burden 4. promoting market innovation and vitality 5. enhancing the reputation and influence of the local place. Their words conveyed that they considered and cared about what they could give rather than just take. It reflects prosocial values and motivation of entrepreneurship among refugees. The participants also believe that their contribution and their values could be acknowledged by the host society, thus promoting a better integration.

Participant 1: "I like setting up new things new products I like research... We started new project about E-learning and some e-book project. I have a team a software team. We create digital book we called it Rich book... It's very useful for teachers for the lessons... Create my company, growing my company, and also convert it to a big company, hire another people, serve this country in a new way, give opportunity to other people."

Participant 2: "...it's important I will open a business, you are in that local community, you are doing contribution. You are not just taking but also giving... And I do believe if I start to do something good, in terms of business, in terms of my career, people will love me and people will accept me here more than someone who is sitting all day watching Netflix, using their taxes."

Participant 3: "At the age of fifty, I've had a career. It is easier for me at this time to look at other ways I can benefit the society, you know, help out in the society, aside from just making money for myself."

Participant 4: "Scottish borders are famous for producing, manufacturing knitwear, wool and other luxurious fabrics... My business is something which is made here with a long, long history, so my business is about promoting Scotland all over the world. I think of course it will help a lot."

The experience of psychological capital and the entrepreneurship education

The role of psychological capital in entrepreneurship

Generally, the participants think hope, optimism, resilience and self-efficacy are important for life as well as business start-ups. Particularly, they have recognised their own psychological capital during the process of migrating to a new country as a refugee, for “leaving the all of one’s belongings behind and going to a totally new country shows higher level of psychological capital.”

Hope and optimism

For the participants, hope and optimism share much in common. They believe that entrepreneurs will not start their business without hope or optimism. In return, achievements in entrepreneurship add to hope and optimism. Hope and optimism are not wishful thinking but based on the awareness of the reality.

Participant 1: “If you don’t have any hope, you can’t grow because hope is the first, I think. We start with hope for growing your business... Every new customer makes us more hopefully actually, new business... When I finished my first job, project, and the customer was satisfied, I realised this optimistic.”

Participant 2: “I see it one of the most fundamental things in starting any business. Because if you are not optimistic, even no reason to start it.”

Participant 3: “Let’s talk about hope as a positive thinking here, not a wishful thinking.”

Participant 4: “I am very optimistic, but I am also very realistic... For me optimism is [that] it’s no big deal to tell the truth.”

Resilience

Resilience makes a successful entrepreneur. Resilience is about perseverance, trying many ways to achieve one’s goal. It is important to help survive the instability and uncertainty and establish a new life in the host society.

Participant 3: “So resilience is just that ability to persevere until what you believe in your head becomes real.”

Participant 4: “How to survive instabilities. If you’re stable for all your life, something will not be right, something went wrong, because life itself is an unstable thing.”

Participant 5: “If we try every day, finally we can do it. I think every people have special ability.”

Self-efficacy

For the participants, self-efficacy is related with self-awareness of one’s abilities and talents, self-discipline and perseverance; it is a transferable ability that could be applied in daily life and then one’s business.

Participant 1: “It’s very important. It’s related to short-term, middle-term, and long-term goals, and achieve your goals.”

Participant 2: “Like me coming here, being a refugee, I was confident that I’ll make it through. It’s an ability that you achieve something you want to do, you get it.”

Participant 3: “Self-efficacious means that you have learned to become effective in the little things in life which you can now transfer to your business.”

Participant 5: “If I think we can, so we can. If we give up, we can’t. I think if I try and don’t give up, I can do it.”

PsyCap can be obtained by learning and life experience

According to the participants, both nature and nurture are believed important for the development of PsyCap; it is more of a skill, knowledge and capability that can be developed through life experience.

Participant 1: “the second one, can be developed by life experience. Some people earn this ability. If you want, you can learn this kind of ability.”

Participant 2: “I think that both are correct because some are born with it already. Some are born emotionally strong, confident; others they are taught by life experiences.”

Participant 3: “I personally believe that if you don’t have those elements in your DNA, it’s very difficult to fake that. At the same time, not everyone that has those elements in them that become an entrepreneur, because maybe their environment is not as helpful as that of the others.”

Participant 4: “I think it’s a skill. I am not sure about if we are born with this, we have it from the beginning I’m not sure. It’s quite difficult. But I know how to gain these skills.”

Entrepreneurship education: The Blue Social Growth programme

The Blue Social Growth training programme comprised four parts: (a) assets, visions and personal passions/ aspirations; (b) money and resource flow in the local economy; (c) opportunities and commitments; and (d) presenting one’s initiative.

The workshop provided an opportunity for the latent entrepreneurs to present one’s idea in front of other people and collect feedback, which “was like a rehearsal of business plan.” The reactions and feedback from the audience gave hope and optimism to the presenter. Besides, the participants also found helpful information provided by the workshop, which might help them analyse the situation better. From these two perspectives, the workshop might have a positive influence on the psychological capital of the refugees with entrepreneurship intentions or those who were working on developing a business start-up.

Participant 1: “The end of the part is good for me because there is useful knowledge in the last one hour, business plan and also they gave some resources of benefits and grants for business.”

Participant 2: “I think it’s great and more information could be collected because we know how things work around here and more essentially things can be done to improve the local community to make the community prosperous more.”

Participant 4: “Because after that, you start thinking about that. And they gave you this optimism because they sound very positive like they accept everything you say, and it helps a lot just because it gives you hope.”

Participant 5: “I think it’s really good for my confident. Because before I am really shy. I think ‘Oh no here I can’t work with art.’ But after the workshop I can understand I can again start for art. Maybe not soon but finally I can.”

DISCUSSION

This study explores three key questions: (1) What are the experiences of refugees engaging in entrepreneurship in the host country? (2) How do refugees perceive and utilise psychological capital in their business ventures? (3) What are their experiences of participating in the Blue Social Growth Project?

The findings reveal several important insights. First, refugee entrepreneurs encounter both challenges and opportunities when starting their businesses. Their rich experiences and high levels of psychological capital serve as competitive assets, while the lack of social networks in the host country presents a significant disadvantage. Transition stress following their arrival is a common issue, and starting a business is seen as a valuable strategy to address these challenges. For those with entrepreneurial aspirations, it facilitates career planning and eases the transition into a new environment.

Second, psychological capital plays a crucial role in both integration and business start-up efforts. The participants' experiences highlight the presence of hope, optimism, self-efficacy, and resilience, which are key components of psychological capital.

Third, the entrepreneurship workshop appears to positively influence participants' psychological capital. This impact may be achieved through the business plan presentation component, which serves three primary functions: helping participants identify and leverage their own assets alongside resources available in the local community, providing valuable information on entrepreneurship, such as funding opportunities, and acting as an open platform for sharing and refining their business ideas.

Transition stress and self-worth

Profession disruption and the resulting threatened self-worth can be a crisis for refugees in the first one or two years since their arrival in the host country. During this transition period of identity, life and work, the refugees are confronted with various problems to solve, and stress may come from language learning, networking, job hunting, family responsibility, etc. Unlike young refugee job seekers whose transition stress mainly comes from lack of work experience prior to migrating and vocational skills (Centre for Multicultural Youth, 2008), the entrepreneurs and potential entrepreneurs, most of them middle-aged, have gained rich experience in their field of speciality before migration. However, occupational experience does not guarantee them an equivalent salaried job in the local labour market due to various reasons including lower language proficiency, inequality and hidden discrimination, and different standards or qualifications of the local vocational system (Bloch, 2007).

For these highly experienced and educated individuals, when they fail to find an equivalent salaried job, they have to choose to upgrade their qualifications according to the requirements of the local labour market (Mulvey, 2015), apply for positions that they are overqualified for (Vinokurov et al., 2017), start their own business (Raijman & Tienda, 2003) or stay unemployed. Loss of previous career threatened self-worth and identity (Luimpöck, 2019). The resulting discrepancy in aspirations and achievements can lower individual's self-esteem (Bhugra, 2004) and threaten their self-identities as professionals in their field of speciality (Wehrle et al., 2018). Self-actualisation and self-worth related themes occurred in all of the interviews, although no interview questions specifically focused on this. They were frequently narrated and identified in the context of career and integration, when talking about personal achievement, professional skills and envision of integration.

Under the motivation of self-actualisation, the refugees have made great efforts. As is mentioned above, the entrepreneurs and latent entrepreneurs have accumulated rich working experience in a specific domain, which helps them know where their talents, capabilities and passions lie and what career they would like to pursue in a new society. For example, although all the participants have gained their college degree in their country of origin, four of the five participants still have chosen to

go to a local college to acquire an academic background acknowledged by the local society, language improvement, networking opportunities, a better understanding of the local economy and policy, etc. Their choice could be supported by the previous findings that educational qualifications gained in the country of origin have no effect on entrepreneurship (Williams & Krasniqi, 2018), while the host country-specific education is positively related to the chances of employment and occupational status (de Vroome & van Tubergen, 2010).

Entrepreneurship and integration

Entrepreneurship is expected to be an effective long-term solution to the resettlement of refugees in addition to short-term problems after forceable movements (UNCTAD, 2018). One of the reasons could be that refugees are more deeply and actively integrating into the host society through entrepreneurship in the light of its positive impact on self-actualisation, contribution to the society and networks. Entrepreneurship provides a good opportunity for self-actualisation for refugees. Self-actualisation is expressed as one of the major expectations and motivations for business start-ups of refugee business owners and latent entrepreneurs. The result is in line with the previous findings that people with higher entrepreneurial intentions took their business as a method to achieve self-esteem and self-actualisation (Carland Jr et al., 1995). It also appears to be the key component shared by transition stress, entrepreneurship and integration. While employment, education, housing and health serve as marks and means of integration (Ager & Strang, 2004; Relojo-Howell, 2024), a new self-realisation in the host society could be the real destination of integration after the transition issues have been solved and could only be measured by the refugees themselves.

Along with self-actualisation, making contribution to the host country with one's own business is also a commonly shared goal of refugee entrepreneurs. This prosocial tendency may indicate their expectation of being accepted and acknowledged by the host society, considering that human prosocial behaviour is more likely to happen when it enables an individual to belong to one's culture and benefit from this belonging (Twenge et al., 2007). It is contradictory to previous evidence that the entrepreneurs did not regard their business as a validation of social acceptance considering their internal locus of control which made them value self-esteem more than social acceptance (Carland Jr et al., 1995). The conflict might be explained by the unprivileged situation of the refugee group. In the host country, the non-dominant minority group are more likely to acculturate to the dominant group to achieve integration (Berry, 1997). The refugees might hope to integrate into the host community by virtue of their business.

Networking and mutual understanding with the local people is a significant reward of entrepreneurship and a vital condition for integration, while lacking in local networks could be a disadvantage for business start-ups. There is research showing that in the UK, immigrants, including refugees, who have networks of the same culture of origin are more likely to set up their own businesses with resources and information from their ethnicity (Levie, 2007). However, the experience of the participants in this research seems not to correspond with Levie's findings perhaps because of the specific domains. Art, fashion, accounting and IT industry are highly demanding areas in terms of academic training and personal skills. Considering the refugees' employment rate of 25% in their first 5 years after arrival in Europe (Dumont et al., 2016) and the likelihood of entering those areas with lower barriers to entry, lower investment and high competition (Wauters & Lambrecht, 2006), it could be inferred that a more limited number of refugees, if any, have entered into these highly demanding fields and build their ethnic co-networks.

Psychological capital and entrepreneurship education

Hope, optimism, self-efficacy and resilience play their part in every aspect of the refugees' new life such as entrepreneurship, communication with the local people, application for college, etc. Many of them have identified their special moment of psychological capital in the process of displacement and resettlement.

Psychological capital (PsyCap) was identified by participants as a crucial factor for entrepreneurship, aligning with findings from previous studies (Labys et al., 2017; Lavie-Ajayi & Slonim-Nevo, 2017). Resilience, in particular, was emphasised as critical for entrepreneurs, given the expectation to persevere under high-risk and resource-constrained conditions. Participants with entrepreneurial experience noted that PsyCap equips individuals to navigate both life and business challenges effectively. They also highlighted its importance for refugee entrepreneurs, who face significant barriers and obstacles during integration into the local economy.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that engaging in work and activities aimed at improving economic status not only fulfils financial needs but also enhances psychological well-being. This improvement stems from the positive impact on self-identity and the fostering of hope, a key component of PsyCap (Labys et al., 2017; Lavie-Ajayi & Slonim-Nevo, 2017; Muhwezi & Sam, 2004; Pavlish, 2005; Segal et al., 2018; Tippens, 2017).

Participants in this research highlighted the adaptability of PsyCap, observing that it can be cultivated through life experiences. This aligns with growing evidence suggesting that PsyCap's components are state-like rather than fixed personality traits, making them amenable to development (Luthans et al., 2008). For example, while hope and optimism tend to remain stable over time and across contexts, they can be adjusted to some extent (Phillips & Gully, 1997; Schulman et al., 1993; Valle et al., 2006). Peterson et al. (1993) proposed that individuals operate within fixed ranges of optimism, but with training, they can consistently experience the higher end of their range. Similarly, self-efficacy can increase through experience, practice, and external influences, such as guidance from others (Luthans et al., 2015).

Participants gained hope, optimism and confidence from the entrepreneurship workshop. The benefits of education and vocational training have been highlighted for their significance (Akinyemi et al., 2016; Cohen & Asgary, 2016; Labys et al., 2017; Lavie-Ajayi & Slonim-Nevo, 2017; Muhwezi & Sam, 2004). Engaging in educational activities, acquiring new skills, and studying were linked to personal development, greater self-reliance, and a more hopeful outlook. These elements were also key in boosting self-confidence and helping refugees build stronger personal narratives (Lavie-Ajayi & Slonim-Nevo, 2017). According to the representative techniques of psychological capital management proposed by Luthans and Youssef (2004), the workshop may have developed self-efficacy and confidence through the technique of “positive feedback” (Part 4: presentation of business plan), hope through “mental rehearsals” (Part 4: presentation of business plan), optimism through “appreciation for the present” (Part 1: pay attention to the assets of one's own and from the environment) and “opportunity-seeking for the future” (Part 3: seek business opportunities from the local community). Overall, the workshop could be helpful to the participants, but it also should be noted that people in different stage of entrepreneurship focused on and valued different part of the workshop (objective information or subjective encourage), indicating their different expectations and needs of support. This is also consistent with the UNCTAD guide of tailored education and support for refugee entrepreneurship (UNCTAD, 2018).

STRENGTHS & LIMITATIONS

The strengths of this research include: a) it focuses on the strengths of the refugees, i.e. their psychological capital and entrepreneurship, which is common among studies on refugees; b) a vivid image of the refugees, which might be different from the perception of the public, was drawn through the in-dept interviews, that all refugees are not poorly-educated and less capable in the labour market.

Limitation of this research mainly lies in the language. The number of participants sample was limited by the language barrier. This also influence the homogeneity of the sample, as it was described in the method section, two of them were already working on self-employment while the other three were not; but all of them had quite clear entrepreneurship intentions or had entrepreneurship experience before migration. The language could also influence the participants' literacy of some terms in the research, such as "integration", "efficacy", "the role of hope", etc, due to ideology in different cultures as well as language proficiency.

The small sample size of five participants could be considered a limitation of this study, affecting the generalisability of the findings. It should be noted that generalisability is not a function of qualitative research. In addition, the small sample size aligns with the methodological approach of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), which prioritises depth over breadth. IPA advocates for smaller samples to facilitate a detailed exploration of individual experiences and meanings, providing rich, qualitative insights from each participant. Smith et al., (1999) recommend smaller samples for IPA to uncover complex, nuanced insights, ensuring a thorough engagement with each participant's narrative.

The diversity among participants in terms of backgrounds, professions, and stages of entrepreneurship enriches the analysis. This diversity is crucial for understanding the unique challenges and assets each participant brings to the entrepreneurial landscape. Acknowledging this allows us to appreciate the varied pathways adopted by refugee entrepreneurs in Scotland. Future research could expand on these findings with a larger, more varied sample to explore these dynamics further.

IMPLICATIONS

Nonetheless, this research investigation could have a significant impact on fostering refugee entrepreneurship and supporting their integration into the host society. More specifically, there are many recommendations that derive from this research which could contribute to a multi-faceted approach to empower refugees that involves policymakers, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and the development of entrepreneurship programmes. In particular, policymakers can create targeted policies to create frameworks that acknowledge refugee entrepreneurship as an integration tool and enhance access to financial resources, such as grants and loans that are designed specifically for refugee entrepreneurs. Additionally, policies that streamline bureaucratic processes around the formalisation of businesses and promote networking opportunities by initiating programmes that increase mentorship opportunities and connect refugees with local business communities could help ease the challenges faced by refugees. NGOs could help refugees by addressing specific needs such as providing access to psychological support to help them with the experience of transition stress and the development of strength characteristics, such as resilience. Furthermore, non-governmental organisations could offer tailored educational programmes that aim to assist in language learning, cultural differences, and other skills training in order to increase their employability. Lastly, entrepreneurship support programmes could be developed to enable refugees to build psychological capital, provide training that is tailored to the local economic needs and facilitate access to information that will help them launch their businesses. Overall, by implementing these recommendations, a more robust and inclusive ecosystem for refugee entrepreneurs could be created.

CONCLUSION

Refugees are likely to experience transmission stress after resettling in the host society and unemployment contributes much. Entrepreneurship can be helpful for the refugees to integrate into the host society, though it might be the only choice for them to have work. Considering the scarcity of longitudinal research on the entrepreneurship of refugees, follow-up research could be done to show how their business goes in the host society. In addition, quantitative research will be helpful in showing the level of psychological capital of latent refugee entrepreneurs and its relation with entrepreneurship.

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